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THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ECONOMIC DIPLOMACY: A CASE OF INDONESIA'S ECONOMIC DIPLOMACY TOWARD EUROPEAN UNION

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Abstract

A country's economic development depends on the strength of its economic diplomacy. This article aims to explore how effective the impact of Indonesia's economic diplomacy towards the European Union is in the export sector. This paper uses qualitative research, with descriptive analysis methods. Data was obtained through a study of literature and documents relating to diplomatic relations in the export sector between Indonesia and the European Union. The results of this research show that various data show a decline in cooperation in the export sector in 2011 and 2012.

Key words: diplomacy, economy, effectiveness.

Introduction

Economic diplomacy is the use of international political tools to engage in economic policies and trade agreement (Yakop and Van Bergeijk 2009). The concept of economic diplomacy usually employs economic resources, both rewards and sanctions, to achieve foreign policy objectives (Berridge and James 2001). This concept is interchangeable with commercial diplomacy which is the action of diplomatic mission in support of home country's business and finance sectors to pursue economic success and national development (Berridge and James 2001). According to Naray (2008), state

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representatives in commercial diplomacy can be both diplomats and professional commercial diplomats. Hence, the definition and the practice of economic diplomacy and commercial diplomacy is not much different, I will use economic diplomacy as the term to cover both economic and commercial diplomacy.

The role of economic diplomacy as an effective instrument in trade has been the subject of economists. Yakop and Bergeijk 2009 argue that the role of economic diplomacy is crucial mainly for developing countries due to asymmetrical information and knowledge between developed and developing countries, less developed institutions, and less transparent of market information in developing countries. The findings show that embassies and consulates have significant and large effects on trade elasticities. But, the effect of economic diplomacy to enhance trade shows negative outcomes within upper middle-income and high-income countries. Furthermore, (van Veenstra et al. 2010) repeated the study of the effect of economic diplomacy on trade in the south. They look at the phenomenon of promotion agencies as the institutions which promote export in developing countries. The promotion agencies are assumed as lack of effectiveness, funds, and business orientation. Veenstra et al conclude that trade promotion agencies do not have positive interaction to improve trade. On the other hand, Hogan et al (1991) pointed out that economic diplomacy through export promotion activities were ineffective to increase trade if there is insufficient finance, less leadership, and lack of experience and training of commercial diplomats.

This essay will examine the effectiveness of economic diplomacy to enhance Indonesia's export in European Union using the gravity model of international trade. The result found that Instruments of economic diplomacy including trade attaché, Indonesia Trade Promotion Centre, and State Visit, do not significantly contribute to boost Indonesia's export to EU from 2009 to 2015. This essay will be organized into four sections. Section 1 is a brief introduction of the topic. Section 2 is the theoretical framework. Section 3 elaborates the empirical finding from previous research in Indonesia, and the final section is the conclusion and summary of the result.

Theoretical Model

The gravity model is used to assess the effect of economic policy on the trade. The model was originally introduced by Tinbergen (1962) in his shaping of the world Economy. The gravity model has been used to estimate the volume of international trade between two countries where the volume of trade is proportional to the product of the index of economic size, and hence the factor of proportionality depends on trade resistance between them (Tinbergen 1962 cited in Helpman et al. 2008).

Bergeijk and Brakman (2010) consider gravity model is the reliable approach to analyze trade policy. Gravity model has been used among policy makers because its robustness and its versatile concept to analyze all kind of trade policy issues. Furthermore, since the equation could be derived from almost international trade model, and it does not give the place to examine among theories, gravity model is becoming more popular. However, it has ambivalent reputation among economists due to lack of a convincing equation and ambiguous micro-economic foundation. It is probably useful as empirical tool, but unfortunately it is unsatisfactory from theoretical concept.

The early version of gravity equation was draw by Linnemann (1966) which become the standard reference of gravity equation. The bilateral trade between countries i and j is symbolized as T_{ij} . The bilateral trade is positively correlated to the economic size of i and j , measured by its GDP. But, the potential flow is reduced by the distance between them (Bergeijk and Brakman 2010). The basic gravity equation is as follows:

$$T_{ij} = \frac{GDP_i^\alpha GDP_j^\beta}{D_{ij}^\theta}$$

This equation explains bilateral trade by using the economic size and distance where the bigger economic size of trading partner, the larger trade flows, and farther the distances between countries, the smaller the bilateral trade (Bergeijk and Brakman 2010).

Meanwhile, extended gravity model which is substituted to international trade include the flow of varying factors such as migration, flow of buyers to shopping center, recreational traffic, commuting, flows of patient from one hospital to others, inter-regional and international trade. The extended gravity model in its form is:

$$X_{ij} = \beta_0 Y_i^{\beta_1} N_i^{\beta_2} Y_j^{\beta_3} Y_j^{\beta_4} D_{ij}^{\beta_5} P_{ij}^{\beta_6}$$

X_{ij} is the value of trade between countries i and j which positively influenced by gross domestic product (Y_k) and size of population (N_k). Furthermore, the bilateral trade is also affected by distance (D_{ij}) and special preference (P_{ij}) between countries i and j (Bikker 1987 cited in Bergeijk and Brakman 2010). However, the gravity model has serious imperfection as claimed by Deardorff (1998). He argues that the derivation of gravity model is less convincing based on economic theory. He examines this argument using Heckscher-Ohlin trade theory under perfect competition, but none of this derivation properly generates gravity model (Deardorff 1998; Bikker 1987; Bergeijk and Brakman 2010).

Empirical Evidences

Many literatures use the gravity model to analyze the effectiveness of economic diplomacy as the instrument to enhance bilateral trade agreement. Rose (2007) analyzes the effect of foreign mission in export. He collected the data from 22 exporting countries and 22 importer countries using gravity model. The result showed that the presence of foreign mission positively linked to country's export where the export tends to increase between 6 and 10 percent for every additional consulate. But, it is still smaller if compare to the effect of language, land border, and regional trade agreement. Furthermore, the result also indicates that the influence of embassy was more significant to improve export than additional consulates.

In the context of Indonesia, Maharani (2015) argue that economic diplomacy which is conducted by Indonesia Trade Promotion Commission (ITPC) and Trade attaché has impact in increase export performance and boosting export promotion. She observed the determinant of trade using gravity model of international trade. Indeed, the finding confirms that economic diplomacy from ITPC successfully accelerate non-oil export of Indonesia. However, the result indicates that the magnitude ITPC is less significant as it brings a small impact on trade performance. On the other hand, the presence of embassy and consulate does not imply the implication to export performances, even it reaches positive yield.

However, Head and Ries (2010) has the adverse result. They use Canadian trade mission to prove the claim that official business mission successfully generated tens of billions of dollars through new business deal. The analysis reveal that trade mission has no significant influence to increase export because Canadian export was already higher prior the mission. Volve et al. (2010) also found that the increase of facilitation on trade such as advising exporter, trade fair and trade mission are positively correlated to improve export, but it seems that building the linkage between exporters and importers in host country are more significant than conducted trade mission.

Result and Discussion

1. Instruments of Economic Diplomacy

The instrument of economic diplomacy in term of economic relation between Indonesia and European Union can be divided into three component, including embassy and consulate, state visit and export promotion activities (Bergeijk).

a. State Visit

State visit are crucial and the most visible instrument to improve relation between countries (Bergeijk). Indonesia government set official state visit to European Union to strengthen trade ties. Since the period of former president Susilo Bambang Yudho Yudhoyono (SBY), Indonesia government officially visited several European countries such as United Kingdom, Germany, and Poland, between 2012 and 2013. These official meeting are not only between government to government, but also between governments to business leaders (Radioaustralia 2012; Republika 2013; Jaringnews 2013).

Furthermore, new ruling government under President Joko Widodo (Jokowi) also strengthened mutual relation through a number of official visit to several European countries including Germany, the UK, Belgium, and the Netherlands in 2016. Since that time, Indonesia established economic diplomacy task force which responsible to coordinate the economic representatives abroad including Trade Attaché and Indonesia Promoting Trade Center (IPTC) (Ministry of Foreign Affairs 2017).

b. Attaché and ITPC

Both institutions ITPC and trade attaché have similar objective to promote export, but different legal status. Trade attaché acts as the

representative of trade minister in abroad, and at same time as the staff of ambassadors, while ITPCs are more informal and does not hold diplomatic status and position. So, that, ITPC is more independent that trade attaché in term of promoting business activities.

Figure 1. Trade Attaché and Indonesia Trade Promotion Center (ITPC)

Source: Ministry of Trade Republic of Indonesia

Indonesia has 44 economic diplomacy instrument spread out in 32 countries, which consists of 25 Trade Attaches and 19 ITPCS. Most of this representative are posted in developed countries especially in European Union where 15 economic diplomacy instruments are in European Union. This is important because Indonesian export in advanced countries is susceptible to get barriers (Ministry of Trade 2017).

These instruments are relevant to improve country's trade and investment for several reasons. Moons et al. (2017) highlight the significant of economic diplomacy into four reasons. First, the influence of government as natural partner in economy is still significant. Second, states companies could become a mutual partner of international companies operating in international markets. Private companies in international market need to improve the mutual relation to the states companies as it probably equalizes the

power balance and levels the playing fields. Third, political uncertainty should be diminished through government involvement as the guarantee of political support. Finally, government officials can access high quality information which simplify international transaction.

However, as Yakop and Bergeijk (2011) highlight that the role of economic diplomacy is more important for developing countries as distribution of knowledge between developing countries and developed countries is still large, so that the instrument is more relevant in North-South and South-North relations. They also observed that trade-related institution in most developing countries less developed and thus government has significant role to deal with it. In contrast, most developed countries have transparent and accessible information, thus it is not relevant to them.

2. Indonesia Export performance to EU

European Union (EU) is the fourth largest trading partner of Indonesia. The biggest share of Indonesia export to EU is mainly from Germany, which has total export USD 2,664 million in 2015 and the smallest was Finland, USD 84.9 million.

Table 1 Total Export Indonesia to European Countries 2009-2015
(Millions USD)

Destination Countries	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
EUROPE							
European Union	13,568.1	17,127.4	20,508.9	18,027.3	16,763.7	16,918.9	14,842.5
the UK	1,459.3	1,693.2	1,719.7	1,696.8	1,634.8	1,658.6	1,527.1
Netherlands	2,909.1	3,722.5	5,132.5	4,664.3	4,106.0	3,984.6	3,442.2
France	870.2	1,122.8	1,284.6	1,128.2	1,062.7	1,019.3	973.0
Germany	2,326.7	2,984.7	3,304.7	3,075.0	2,883.4	2,821.6	2,664.2
Belgium	1,048.3	1,190.1	1,374.7	1,297.7	1,259.3	1,217.3	1,113.3
Denmark	168.8	180.2	250.2	229.4	224.5	226.6	207.0
Sweden	144.3	156.5	170.4	166.3	162.4	177.1	146.8
Finland	61.2	122.7	219.0	197.8	149.1	111.4	84.9
Italy	1,651.1	2,370.0	3,168.3	2,277.0	2,128.6	2,286.9	1,872.9
Spain	1,830.5	2,328.7	2,427.9	2,069.3	1,810.4	1,937.6	1,481.3
Greece	165.7	155.4	157.5	139.9	149.2	157.4	143.9
Poland	259.7	313.3	379.5	340.0	365.4	396.0	358.9
Portugal	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Austria	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ireland	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other EU Countries	673.2	787.3	919.9	745.6	827.9	924.5	827.0
Other Europe	983.5	1,450.7	1,789.7	1,696.9	1,858.7	1,752.7	2,546.0

Sources: Indonesia Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS)

3.The Effectiveness Economic Diplomacy on Export Performance

Indonesia Total Export to EU considerably increase in 2010 by USD 17,127 million, but it continuously declined by USD 14,842 in 2015. The upward trend of total export was showed mostly in 2010 for all countries except Greece which declined by USD 155.4 million. Several countries such as Germany, Italy, and Spain have considerable increased especially in 2010, 2011, and 2012. After 2011, export Indonesia to EU declined because of the Eurozone crisis (Huffington Post 2012).

The number of economic representative in EU increase by the year. Since 2008, the number of Indonesia Trade Promotion Center (ITPC) increased by five which spread out in several cities including Budapest, Milan, Barcelona, Hamburg, and Lyon. The trend of export performance and economic diplomacy instrument in EU show below,

Figure 2 Total Export Indonesia to EU over the increase of country's representatives

Sources: Indonesia Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS) and Ministry of Trade Republic of Indonesia

The trend illustrates that the establishment of trade representatives both trade attaché and IPTC is not in line with the increase of total export in host countries. The pattern of total export from Indonesia to EU continuously decrease since 2008. The great recession was the reason Indonesia-EU total trade declined massively started from third quarter of 2008 through the second quarter of 2009. The decline was the largest in the forty years (Shelburne 2010). At the same time, the number of ITCP were established in several EU countries to advancing Indonesia trade through providing information, professional advice, and services (ITPC Hamburg 2017). Nowadays, Indonesia has 15 economic diplomacy instruments in EU, of which 10 are the trade attaché and 5 are ITPC (Ministry of Trade 2017).

Moreover, a series of official visits from 2012, 2013, and 2016 has similar result to other diplomacy instruments. Indonesia's export was continuous decline since 2012 to 2015. The finding show that economic diplomacy through trade attaché, ITPC or official government visiting do not effectively relevant to enhance trade ties between Indonesia and EU.

Conclusion

In this essay, I started by outlining the question about the effectiveness economic diplomacy to enhance Indonesia's export to European Union (EU). In the context of Indonesia, several instruments conduct economic diplomacy such as trade attaché, Indonesia Trade Promotion Centre (ITPC), and official visit from president. Furthermore, recently Indonesia also recognize the institution known as economic diplomacy task force under ministry of foreign affairs which focus on coordination among institutions to enhance national trade and investment. Indonesia has increase the number of instruments to boost Indonesia export through penetration, information, dissemination, actively participate in international exhibition, also to assist Indonesia companies expanding trade.

Indonesia export to EU continuously decline especially since the debt crisis in 2011 and 2012. At the same time, Indonesia also increase the ITPC in several countries, and actively build the mutual relation through official visits. Since 2008, there are 15 trade mission in European Union, and there was there time official visit to EU. But, the result show Indonesia export value was not going in line with the increase trade mission and official visit from government. Indeed, the export continuously decline until 2015. Hence, the outcome of this essay may encourage government to find the appropriate policy particularly to support Indonesia companies abroad. Government probably can reduce bureaucracy procedure, transparent for information, and improving coordination among the trade missions.

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